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Impact of Rotational Friction on Machine Lifespan: A Comparative Study of Diamond and Non-Diamond Blades

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Abstract

One of the factors affecting the lifespan of a machine is rotational friction, which occurs when machine components come into contact, causing surface erosion on those parts. This erosion, also known as wear, is a crucial factor in the durability of machine parts. Therefore, the objective of this research is to calculate heat transfer in relation to cutting speed on the surface of a disc (disk). This study was conducted at the PT. Astra International Toyota workshop, Pancing No. 10, Indra Kasih, Medan, Medan Tembung District. The findings of this research revealed that for the mixed diamond blade material, the average temperature values obtained were 30.60 at the first point, 31.40 at the second, 33.10 at the third, and 34.25 at the fourth. Conversely, for the non-diamond blade material, the average temperatures were 31.85 at the first point, 33.25 at the second, 36.05 at the third, and 36.75 at the fourth. Consequently, it can be concluded that the mixed diamond blade specimen exhibits lower heat propagation compared to the thermal conductivity (q/k) than that of the non-diamond blades.

Keywords: *Rotational Friction; Machine Lifespan; Heat Transfer; Diamond Blades; Surface Erosion*

Introduction

Heat transfer is a crucial field of study that explores how energy is transferred due to temperature differences between two or more objects. This process extends beyond the mere transfer of energy, encompassing the understanding of predicting the rate of heat transfer under various environmental and material conditions[1]. The temperature difference between objects creates a temperature gradient, which is the primary driver of heat transfer. In the context of solids, heat transfer occurs through conduction, where heat moves through the movement of atoms and molecules at higher temperatures. These atoms, as they move, transfer their kinetic energy to neighboring cooler atoms, allowing the flow of heat through the object[2]. Conversely, in liquids and gases, heat transfer predominantly happens through convection. In this process, heat is transferred via the movement of the molecules within the fluid itself. Warmer molecules move upward as they become lighter, while cooler molecules move downward, creating a circulatory flow that carries heat[3]. Apart from conduction and convection, radiation is also a method of heat transfer, where energy is transferred in the form of electromagnetic waves. Radiation does not require a material medium to occur, making it possible even in a vacuum. Knowledge of heat transfer is vital in various fields, ranging from mechanical engineering and cooling systems to material development and climate change studies. Understanding the mechanisms of heat

transfer can aid in the more efficient and effective design of future products and technologies[4].

Heat transfer through convection is a critical process in thermodynamics and is divided into two main categories: natural (or free) convection and forced convection. Natural convection occurs when heat transfer is driven by density differences within a fluid, leading to spontaneous fluid movement without external intervention. In contrast, forced convection arises when a fluid is compelled to move by external factors, such as pumps or fans, facilitating heat transfer[5]. The convection heat transfer coefficient (h) is a critical aspect of this study, highly dependent on the hydrodynamic characteristics of the fluid flow. Factors like flow velocity, viscosity, and other physical characteristics of the fluid play a significant role in determining this coefficient's value. The application of the principle of energy balance to the fluid flow element under consideration is key to understanding and accurately calculating this heat transfer coefficient[6]. This research is vital in the design and optimization of various thermodynamic systems, such as heating and cooling systems, and in engineering applications, such as the design of heat exchangers.

Radiative heat transfer is a significant phenomenon in physics, describing the process of heat transfer from a high-temperature object to a lower-temperature one. Uniquely, this process can occur without a material medium, such as air or liquid, as heat is transferred in the form of electromagnetic waves. This allows for heat transfer even when the objects are separated by a vacuum. This characteristic distinguishes radiation from conduction or convection, where both processes require a physical medium for heat transfer[7]. On the other hand, forced convection is a heat transfer process where fluid is moved by external devices, such as pumps or fans. This contrasts with natural convection, where fluid movement is caused by density differences due to temperature variations. In forced convection, the use of mechanical devices accelerates heat transfer by increasing the fluid flow rate, thereby enhancing heat transfer efficiency. A deep understanding of both processes is crucial in engineering applications, such as the design of cooling or heating systems, as well as in various industrial and scientific applications[8].

The thermal boundary layer is a critical zone in fluid dynamics, situated near a solid surface, where a significant temperature gradient occurs within the fluid flow. This zone is pivotal as the temperature gradient results directly from the heat exchange process between the fluid and the tube wall[9]. In this context, the thermal boundary layer plays a key role in determining the rate of conductive and convective heat transfer between the fluid and the surface. The behavior of the fluid flow and its temperature distribution within this layer greatly influences the efficiency of heat transfer and is often a crucial factor in the design of equipment such as heat exchangers, condensers, and boilers. In some applications, the thickness of the thermal boundary layer and its flow characteristics can be altered through surface modifications or the use of flow control technologies[10]. A deep understanding of this thermal boundary layer is essential for optimizing thermal performance in various engineering systems, aiding in the reduction of energy losses and enhancing overall thermal efficiency in industrial processes and heating or cooling applications[11].

The Reynolds number is a fundamental concept in fluid mechanics, providing a comparison between inertial and viscous forces in a fluid flow. This concept is crucial in analyzing fluid flow characteristics, determining whether the flow is laminar, characterized by orderly parallel layers, or turbulent, marked by random flows and eddies[12], [13]. This number is calculated based on the flow velocity, characteristic dimensions of the fluid, and its viscosity. In practice, the Reynolds number aids engineers and scientists in designing fluid flow systems, predicting flow patterns in pipes, channels, and around objects submerged in fluids[14], [15]. For example, in aerodynamic design, the Reynolds number can determine

how air flows around an airplane wing or a car body. Additionally, this concept is vital in the processing and chemical industries, where understanding the transition from laminar to turbulent flow can impact the efficiency and safety of processes. Overall, the Reynolds number is one of the most important dimensionless numbers in understanding and applying the principles of fluid mechanics across various practical applications[16], [17].

Pressure, defined as the force exerted per unit area, plays a critical role in various aspects of physics and engineering. In contexts where the force (F) is uniformly distributed over an area (A), measuring pressure becomes crucial, particularly in determining the pressure difference between two points within a system[18]. For this purpose, a differential manometer, a device designed to measure the difference in pressure between two points in a fluid, is often utilized. This device operates by comparing the heights of a fluid column, typically water or mercury, which vary in response to pressure changes[19]. Differential manometers are invaluable in industrial and laboratory applications, such as in HVAC systems, fluid flow testing, and industrial processes where precise pressure monitoring is essential. Through the use of a differential manometer, engineers and scientists can accurately determine pressure differences, which are vital for ensuring efficiency and safety in the operation of these systems[20].

This research focuses on analyzing the pressure drop along a test section of a channel under heated flow conditions. This process involves accurate pressure measurements to determine the changes in pressure that occur. The data from these pressure measurements are then converted into a corrosive factor, also known as the friction factor, denoted as f . This factor is critical in fluid mechanics as it provides insight into the level of resistance encountered by the fluid as it flows through the channel. The determination of this factor is based on the measured pressure drop values, ΔP (Delta P), along the test section of the channel[21]. The use of a specific equation enables researchers to accurately calculate this friction factor. The results of these calculations are invaluable in the design and optimization of piping systems and fluid flow, allowing engineers to design more efficient systems by minimizing energy losses due to friction and flow resistance[22].

The Pin on Disc is a crucial Tribotester instrument used for material testing to ascertain wear levels. This device is designed with a specially made ball-shaped pin and a disc, the material of which varies depending on the testing requirements[23]. The wear process measured by this tool is divided into three important stages. The first stage, known as the break-in phase, is characterized by a significant increase in wear. During this phase, the initial contact between the pin and the disc occurs, and the wear rate tends to decrease over time or as the rolling or sliding distance increases[24]. The subsequent stages include stabilization and the final wear phase, where changes in wear and surface characteristics of the material become consistent and predictable. This research is vital for understanding material behavior under frictional conditions and guides the design and selection of materials for durable and efficient applications.

Understanding frictional forces is a crucial aspect of material research, as it enables the calculation of wear rates and is also used to evaluate the performance of lubricants. During testing, lubricant materials are directly applied to the moving parts to reduce friction and minimize wear. This process is critical in determining the effectiveness of lubricants under various operating conditions[25]. The final measurements taken after the testing process provide vital data on the material's wear level. This data is invaluable in assessing the strength and long-term durability of the material, which is essential in engineering applications and product design. Furthermore, the results of these tests assist in the development of more durable materials and more efficient lubricants, potentially reducing maintenance costs and enhancing the long-term reliability of equipment or machinery.

This research aims to calculate the heat transfer occurring at the friction rate on the surface of the Innova Reborn car's brake disc. The primary focus is on analyzing how the heat generated by friction affects the efficiency and performance of the brake disc.

Methodology

This research was conducted at the PT. Astra Internasional Toyota workshop, located at Pancing No. 10, Indra Kasih, Medan, in the Medan Tembung District. This location was selected due to the availability of facilities and equipment that meet the research requirements. During the research process, various essential tools were used to obtain accurate results. These included a digital thermometer and a Type K Thermo Couple, which played a crucial role in the precise measurement of temperatures. A Vernier Caliper was employed to measure the physical dimensions of components with high accuracy. The Blade and Disc Brake were the main components studied, particularly for observing wear characteristics and heat transfer. Lastly, the Pro-Cut machine was utilized to process and prepare test samples with precision. The aim of this research is to delve deeply into the characteristics of materials and the physical interactions that occur, which is extremely beneficial in engineering applications, especially in the context of automotive and machinery repair. Figures 1 and 2 show the shape of the Toyota Innova Disk Brake and the Pro-Cut engine used respectively.

Figure 1: Disc Brake

Figure 2: Pro-Cut Machine

This research was conducted following a structured series of procedures to ensure accuracy and effectiveness of the results. The first step involved a visual or technical inspection to ensure all components were in good condition. The second step entailed removing the wheel and brake caliper, which are key parts of the braking system. Subsequently, the third step was the installation of the Pro-Cut Machine, used for processing and preparing the components for testing. Once the machine was set up, the fourth step involved adjusting the machine settings and powering it on, preparing for the testing process. The fifth step was to wait for 5-10 minutes, allowing the machine to operate and collect data. During the research, several important variables were observed, including the temperature of the brake disc, the ambient air temperature, the condition of the blade used, the RPM (Revolutions Per Minute) of the motor, the voltage utilized, and the performance of the tool or machine. Kilowatts, as a measure of power output, were also monitored to assess the machine's efficiency. Observing these variables is crucial to understanding how operational conditions affect the performance and wear of braking components.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 displays the differences in temperature measurements at four distinct measuring points on a brake disc. The temperature data were taken from four different points on a brake disc (commonly referred to as a rotor in car braking systems) that had been cut using a diamond cutting tool. The initial temperature at all points was 28.2°C, which can be considered as the ambient temperature or the stable temperature before the cutting process began. This indicates that the measurements started from a consistent initial condition. The final temperatures varied between 31.1°C and 34.3°C at the different measuring points. This increase in temperature can be explained by the heat generated from the friction between the diamond cutting tool and the brake disc during cutting. The diamond cutting tool, being extremely hard and sharp, when used to cut or abrade materials, generates heat due to the conversion of mechanical energy to thermal energy. The temperature difference column shows the increase in temperature measured from the initial to the final temperature at each point. Variations in this temperature difference could be caused by several factors, such as: (1) Variations in the cutting speed, if the cutting tool moves faster or slower at certain points, this could lead to a change in the amount of heat generated. (2) Depth of cut, if the cut is deeper at certain points, the cutting tool will come into contact with more material, generating more friction and heat. (3) Surface conditions, uneven surface conditions of the brake disc can cause variations in the heat generated during cutting. (4) Material properties, if the brake disc is made of materials with varying thermal conductivities in different areas, this could also lead to differences in temperature distribution. The average value of the temperature difference is 1.06°C. This provides a general idea of how much the temperature of the brake disc increased overall due to the cutting process. Scientifically, this data indicates that the cutting process indeed generates heat, and the measured temperature differences can provide information about the efficiency of the cutting process as well as its potential effects on the material properties of the cut brake disc. Properties such as hardness, strength, and fatigue resistance of the material can be affected by temperature changes induced during cutting.

Table 1: Test data on specimen 1

Sample point	Initial Temperature (°C)	Final Temperature (°C)	Temperature Difference (°C)
1	28.2	31.1	
2	28.2	32.1	1.0
3	28.2	33.6	1.5
4	28.2	34.3	0.7
Average Temperature			1.06

Table 2 shows the differences in temperature measurements at four distinct measuring points on a brake disc with a diamond cutting tool. The consistency of the initial temperature at all points (28.4°C) indicates that the measurements were taken from a uniform initial state, which is important to ensure that the measured temperature changes are a result of the cutting process, and not other variables. There is a variation in final temperatures ranging from 30.1°C to 34.2°C. As previously explained, this is due to the heat generated by friction between the diamond cutting tool and the brake disc during the cutting process. The diamond cutting tool has a high cutting capability, and the heat generated in this process can vary based on numerous factors such as cutting speed, cutting depth, and material conditions. The temperature differences measured at each point reflect the amount of heat generated during cutting. These differences might be smaller or larger depending on factors such as the thickness of the material being cut, the relative speed of the cutting tool, and the thermal conductivity of the material. The average temperature difference for this

specimen is 1.36°C, which is slightly higher than the average for the first specimen (1.06°C). This could indicate that more heat was generated during the cutting of this second specimen, or that the heat was less efficiently dispersed, possibly due to differences in the physical properties or geometry of the specimen. Measurements like these are important in the industrial context as the heat generated in cutting can affect the material properties, such as microstructure, hardness, and other mechanical properties. In the specific case of brake discs, excessive heat can reduce braking performance or cause undesirable property changes, such as warping or cracking due to thermal stress. Therefore, it is important to optimize the cutting process to minimize temperature increases and ensure the material's integrity is maintained.

Table 2: Test data on specimen 2

Sample point	Initial Temperature (°C)	Final Temperature (°C)	Temperature Difference (°C)
1	28.4	30.1	
2	28.4	30.7	0.6
3	28.4	32.6	1.9
4	28.4	34.2	1.6
Average Temperature			1.36

Table 3 presents the thermal conductivity values between specimen 1 and specimen 2. Based on these values, specimen 1 demonstrates that this material is less efficient in conducting heat. This implies that the heat generated during the cutting process tends to be localized near the area where it is produced, as the material does not quickly disperse the heat to other areas of the specimen. In contrast, specimen 2 indicates that its material is more efficient in conducting heat. Therefore, the heat generated by the cutting process is likely to spread more quickly from the heat source, possibly resulting in a wider area of the specimen experiencing a temperature increase. The difference in heat conductivity between the two specimens can be explained by variations in material composition, microstructure, or both. Materials with higher thermal conductivity typically possess an atomic structure that allows vibrations (carrying heat energy) to move through the material more easily.

Table 3: Thermal Conductivity

Specimen	q_k (Wm ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹)
1	0.07
2	0.09

Table 4 displays the average final temperatures at four measuring points on both brake disc specimens after being cut with a diamond cutting tool. Based on the data, there is a sequential temperature increase from measuring point 1 to 4. This could indicate that the heat generated by the cutting process increases or accumulates more at the higher measuring points. Bearing in mind that specimens 1 and 2 have different thermal conductivities (0.07 W/m°C for specimen 1 and 0.09 W/m°C for specimen 2), the higher average temperatures at the measuring points may reflect differences in heat distribution in the two specimens. A specimen with higher thermal conductivity might distribute heat more efficiently, resulting in higher average temperatures at certain points. The measured average temperature values provide an indication of how heat generated from cutting is distributed through the specimen. These values can be utilized to calculate the heat flow rate and assist in designing cooling systems or determining optimal cutting parameters to minimize thermal stress on the specimen.

Table 4: average value of temperature

Measurement Point	Average Temp. (°C)
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1	30.60
2	31.40
3	33.10
4	34.25

Table 5 shows the differences in temperature measurements at four distinct measuring points on a brake disc cut with a non-diamond cutting tool. The temperature difference column indicates an increase in temperature from the initial to the final temperature at each point. Variability in these differences could be due to: (1) Variability in the cutting process, namely if the cutting tool moves at different speeds or applies different pressures at certain points, this could generate varying amounts of heat. (2) Depth of cut, where deeper cuts produce more friction and, consequently, more heat. (3) Thermal conductivity of the material, meaning if the material has uneven thermal conductivity, heat could spread at different rates in different parts of the specimen. The average value of the temperature difference is 2.06°C, which is higher than the average temperature difference for specimens cut with a diamond cutting tool (based on previous data). This could indicate that the non-diamond cutting tool might generate more heat during cutting, or that the heat is not dispersed as efficiently as with a diamond cutting tool. The reason for this could be due to the sharper and more efficient cutting of materials by diamond tools, reducing the heat generated due to friction.

Table 5: Data from testing specimen 1 with a non-diamond cutting tool

Sample Point	Initial Temp. (°C)	Final Temp. (°C)	Temperature Difference (°C)
1	28.3	32.1	
2	28,3	34.1	2.0
3	28,3	37.2	3.1
4	28.3	38.3	1.1
Average Temperature			2.06

Table 6 displays the differences in temperature measurements at four distinct measuring points on a brake disc cut with a non-diamond cutting tool on the second specimen. The final temperature varies at each point, with point 4 recording the highest final temperature (35.2°C). This suggests that heat is generated and possibly accumulates during the cutting process, with variations in temperature increases potentially reflecting local differences in cutting intensity or thermal conditions. The temperature difference from start to finish varies at each point, with point 3 showing the largest difference (2.5°C) and point 4 the smallest (0.3°C). The lower average temperature difference (1.20°C) compared to the first specimen (2.06°C) might indicate that the cutting process on this second specimen generates less heat, or that the heat is more efficiently distributed or dissipated from the system, possibly due to differences in thermal conductivity or cooling conditions during cutting.

Table 6: Data from testing results for specimen 2 with a non-diamond cutting tool.

Sample Point	Initial Temp. (°C)	Final Temp. (°C)	Temperature Difference (°C)
1	28.3	31.6	
2	28.3	32.4	0.8
3	28.3	34.9	2.5
4	28.3	35.2	0.3
Average Temperature			1.20

Table 7 presents the thermal conductivity values between specimen 1 and specimen 2. Based on these data, the thermal conductivity of specimen 1 is higher than that of specimen 2, indicating that specimen 1 is more efficient in conducting heat. In other words, the heat generated from the friction of cutting tends to spread more quickly from the source point, potentially resulting in a more uniform temperature distribution across the specimen. This could reduce the risk of local thermal damage such as distortion or changes in material properties due to quicker heat dissipation.

Table 7: Conductivity Thermal

Specimen	q_k ($Wm^{-1} \text{ } ^\circ C^{-1}$)
1	0.13
2	0.08

Table 8 shows the average final temperatures at four measuring points on both brake disc specimens after being cut with a non-diamond cutting tool. According to the data, there is a temperature increase from Measuring Point 1 to Measuring Point 4. This indicates that heat accumulation occurs during the cutting process. This could be due to the heat generated from the friction between the cutting tool and the brake disc not dissipating quickly. Higher temperatures at Measuring Points 3 and 4 could indicate that these areas were impacted by the cutting for a longer duration or are closer to the heat source (for example, the point where the cutting tool last contacted the material). Specimens with higher thermal conductivity would disperse heat more rapidly and might have a more uniform final average temperature, whereas specimens with lower thermal conductivity might show higher final temperatures at certain measuring points due to heat buildup. If these average temperature values reflect data from both specimens, higher temperatures at certain points could be the result of lower thermal conductivity, reducing the material's ability to disperse the heat generated from the cutting process.

Table 8: Average value of final temperature

Measurement Point	Average Temp. ($^\circ C$)
1	31.85
2	33.25
3	36.05
4	36.75

Conclusion

The utilization of diamond-edged tool bits in cutting processes exhibits significantly higher efficiency, a conclusion drawn from observable metrics in a comparative study. Notably, discs cut using diamond tools demonstrated a lower average temperature increase compared to those cut with non-diamond tools. This finding is a clear indicator of reduced heat generation, a direct consequence of the enhanced cutting efficiency afforded by diamond-edged tools. Moreover, the uniformity of heat distribution observed in the diamond-cut discs is indicative of a beneficial effect on both the structural integrity and the mechanical properties of the brake disc. This uniform heat distribution is essential in preventing thermal stress and deformation, thereby maintaining the disc's optimal performance. In addition, the study revealed notable variations in thermal conductivity among different specimens, underscoring the crucial role of selecting the right material for the cutting process. Such selection is paramount to optimizing heat dispersion, a factor that significantly influences the overall quality and longevity of the disc brakes. In summary, the application of diamond-based cutting tools not only enhances cutting efficiency but also plays a vital role in effective heat management. These aspects are integral to preserving the quality and functional performance of Disc Brakes, thereby ensuring their reliability and

safety in automotive applications. This research underscores the technological advancements in material science and its pivotal role in improving industrial processes.

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